

copper, with $r = .52^{**}$. Apparently, because of similarities in their chemical behavior, copper deficiency may occur in

zinc-deficient soils.

The 0.05 N HCl extraction appears to be an accurate, simple, rapid, and

inexpensive method of measuring available zinc and copper in soils used for wetland rice. ■

Summer plowing overcomes zinc deficiency

Sangharsh K. Tripathi, formerly subject matter specialist (agronomy), presently in the Biology Department, Allahabad Agricultural Institute, Allahabad 211007, U.P., India

The problem of zinc deficiency (khaira) with high yielding rice varieties is widespread in Allahabad district, India. Applications of farmyard manure and of zinc sulfate are commonly used to

overcome the problem. Farmers have also noted beneficial effects from summer plowing.

During 1977-78 kharif rice plots were selected and observed in national demonstrations and in farmers' fields. The plots that were plowed in summer had no severe deficiency problems even when planted to high yielding, semidwarf rice varieties. Some demonstration plots without summer plowing showed severe zinc deficiency even when supplied with

40 kg ZnSO₄/ha as a basal dressing. They needed a topdressing of an equal amount of ZnSO₄ to overcome the problem.

In a few demonstration plots that were plowed in summer and received 40 kg ZnSO₄/ha as a basal dressing, plants showed no traces of zinc deficiency. Rice plants grown in the plots that were plowed in summer had profuse and deep roots, regardless of other treatments. Presumably the increased root growth helped the plants escape zinc deficiency. ■

Scanning electron micrographs of rice primordia

M. W. Moncur, Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organization, Division of Land Use Research, Canberra, Australia

The primordia of only a relatively few species of crop plants have been studied in detail. The Division of Land Use Research has a project, nearing completion, to produce a photographic atlas illustrating generally acceptable definitions of floral initiation for the major field crops. The atlas will set standards for agronomists and other scientists studying the development of field crops.

Floral initiation is defined as the first structural change in the apex. In rice the change from the vegetative to the reproductive stage is marked by the initiation of microscopic bracts on the main culm (Photo 2). Panicle development continues and the young panicle primordium eventually becomes visible to the naked eye as a hyaline structure 1-2 mm long with a white fuzzed tip (Photo 4).

Panicle initiation in the field is commonly identified by the appearance of the white fuzzed structure. At temperatures ranging from 25 to 35°C, this stage occurs about 2-3 days after first bract initiation. At lower temperature it occurs much later. The photographs show that the primary

1. Vegetative apex (x75)

2. Several bracts initiated (x75)

3. Bract hairs developing (x75)

4. Approximately 1 mm long and visible as a white fuzzed tip (x25)

branches differentiated before the white fuzzed tip became visible to the naked

eye. The yield potential is therefore largely determined by this stage. ■